

Supplementary Table 1. Sequence number for each virus and dataset

Zika	Dengue	Ebolavirus	HIV1
C (485;53;15)	C (4865;1262;304)	NP (434;95;51)	ENV (6223*;913;913)
pr (485;82;22)	prM (4868;2111;506)	vp35 (434;61;32)	GAG (8534*;815;815)
M (485;89;19)	E (4864;3482;1289)	vp40 (434;51;25)	NEF (6788*;924;924)
E (485;214;57)	NS1 (4864;3058;1103)	GP (186;37;23)	POL (4416*;929;929)
NS1 (485;179;69)	NS2A (4864;2663;973)	sGP (610;76;37)	REV (3529*;859;859)
NS2A (485;156;48)	NS2B (4864;1887;339)	vp30 (434;52;25)	TAT (3366*;845;844)
NS2B (485;94;14)	NS3 (4864;3564;1050)	vp24 (436;53;24)	VIF (4465*;989;989)
NS3 (485;191;52)	NS4A (4864;1984;377)	L (436;169;86)	VPR (4251*;975;974)
NS4A (485;81;15)	NS4B (4864;2565;535)		VPU (5111*;965;964)
NS4B (485;150;45)	NS5 (4863;3820;1803)		
NS5 (485;247;89)			

only sequences without ambiguous nucleotides and in-frame stop codons were used for these calculations. (total number; nucleotide dataset; amino acid dataset); *1000 randomly chosen sequences were selected for downstream analyses.

Supplementary Table 2. Number of positively selected amino acid site per virus, coding region, sequence dataset and replica.

		HIV																		Zika				Ebola virus			
		VPU		VPR		VIF		TAT		REV		POL		NEF		GAG		ENV		NS5		NS4B		NP		sGP	
		M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2	M8	M2
Nucleotide	1	5	5	4	4	8	8	13	12	10	9	17	14	9	9	12	12	64	68	1	1	0	0	1	0	2	2
	2	5	5	10	1	11	10	19	16	7	7	19	14	6	7	11	10	62	58	1	1	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	18	15	8	8	18	15	5	7	12	12	58	64	0	0	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	4	6	6	2	0	8	8	16	16	12	11	20	14	7	5	16	13	45	46	0	0	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	5	6	5	4	3	9	9	20	15	12	12	21	14	7	7	9	9	68	67	1	1	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Average		5.2	5	4.8	2.4	8.2	7.8	17.2	14.8	9.8	9.4	19	14.2	6.8	7	12	11.2	59.4	60.6	0.6	0.6	0	0	1	0	2	2
Amino acid	1	4	4	3	2	11	11	17	17	15	14	21	20	6	6	17	17	72	72	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	2
	2	4	4	7	2	10	9	16	16	10	8	17	13	7	7	11	10	64	63	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	3	5	5	4	4	12	12	15	14	9	9	16	13	7	7	16	16	55	58	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	4	8	8	6	0	7	7	16	15	4	2	15	11	8	8	12	11	66	67	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	5	6	5	3	2	9	10	17	19	13	12	26	22	4	4	11	11	60	63	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Average		5.4	5.2	4.6	2	9.8	9.8	16.2	16.2	10.2	9	19	15.8	6.4	6.4	13.4	13	63.4	64.6	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	2

Supplementary Table 3. Summary of the evidence for recombination for Zika, for each coding region, sequence dataset, and replica. Yellow highlight – Evidence for recombination in the full dataset.

	PhiPack			
	NSS	Chi^2	Phi (permutation)	Phi
A_C	X			
A_E	X	X	X	
A_M	X			
A_NS1		X		
A_NS2A	X	X	X	
A_NS2B	X			
A_NS3	X	X	X	
A_NS4A				
A_NS4B				
A_NS5		X		
A_pr				
N_Zika-C	X			
N_Zika-E_1		X	X	
N_Zika-E_2		X		
N_Zika-E_3		X	X	
N_Zika-E_4		X	X	
N_Zika-E_5	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-M	X			
N_Zika-NS1_1				
N_Zika-NS1_2				
N_Zika-NS1_3				
N_Zika-NS1_4			X	X
N_Zika-NS1_5				
N_Zika-NS2A_1		X	X	
N_Zika-NS2A_2	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS2A_3	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS2A_4	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS2A_5	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS2B_1	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS2B_2			X	
N_Zika-NS2B_3	X		X	
N_Zika-NS2B_4	X		X	
N_Zika-NS2B_5		X	X	
N_Zika-NS3_1	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS3_2	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS3_3	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS3_4	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS3_5	X	X	X	X
N_Zika-NS4A				
N_Zika-NS4B_1				
N_Zika-NS4B_2				
N_Zika-NS4B_3				
N_Zika-NS4B_4				
N_Zika-NS4B_5				
N_Zika-NS5_1				
N_Zika-NS5_2				
N_Zika-NS5_3				
N_Zika-NS5_4	X	X		
N_Zika-NS5_5				
N_Zika-pr				

Supplementary Table 4. Summary of the evidence for recombination for Dengue, for each coding region, sequence dataset, and replica. Yellow highlight – Evidence for recombination in the full dataset.

	PhiPack			
	NSS	Chi ²	Phi (permutation)	Phi
A_C_1		X		
A_C_2		X		
A_C_3	X	X		
A_C_4	X	X		
A_C_5				
A_E_1		X	X	X
A_E_2		X		
A_E_3	X	X	X	X
A_E_4		X	X	X
A_E_5	X	X	X	X
A_NS1_1	X	X		
A_NS1_2	X	X		
A_NS1_3		X		
A_NS1_4	X		X	X
A_NS1_5	X	X		X
A_NS2A_1				
A_NS2A_2				
A_NS2A_3				
A_NS2A_4				
A_NS2A_5				
A_NS2B_1	X			
A_NS2B_2				
A_NS2B_3				
A_NS2B_4				
A_NS2B_5	X		X	X
A_NS3_1				
A_NS3_2				
A_NS3_3				
A_NS3_4				
A_NS3_5				
A_NS4A_1	X			
A_NS4A_2				
A_NS4A_3				
A_NS4A_4		X		
A_NS4A_5				
A_NS4B_1				
A_NS4B_2		X		
A_NS4B_3				
A_NS4B_4	X	X		
A_NS4B_5	X	X		
A_NS5_1	X	X		
A_NS5_2	X		X	X
A_NS5_3	X			
A_NS5_4	X		X	X
A_NS5_5	X	X		
A_prM_1	X	X		
A_prM_2	X	X		
A_prM_3				
A_prM_4				
A_prM_5				
N_C_1	X	X		
N_C_2	X	X		
N_C_3	X			
N_C_4	X	X		
N_C_5	X	X		
N_E_1	X			
N_E_2				
N_E_3	X		X	X
N_E_4	X		X	X
N_E_5	X	X		
N_NS1_1	X		X	X
N_NS1_2	X		X	X
N_NS1_3	X	X	X	X
N_NS1_4			X	X
N_NS1_5	X	X	X	X
N_NS2A_1				
N_NS2A_2				
N_NS2A_3				
N_NS2A_4				
N_NS2A_5				
N_NS2B_1				
N_NS2B_2				
N_NS2B_3				
N_NS2B_4			X	X
N_NS2B_5				
N_NS3_1	X			
N_NS3_2		X		
N_NS3_3				
N_NS3_4				
N_NS3_5			X	X
N_NS4A_1				
N_NS4A_2				
N_NS4A_3	X			
N_NS4A_4				
N_NS4A_5				
N_NS4B_1	X			
N_NS4B_2	X	X		
N_NS4B_3				
N_NS4B_4	X			
N_NS4B_5	X			
N_NS5_1	X			
N_NS5_2		X		
N_NS5_3	X	X		
N_NS5_4	X	X	X	X
N_NS5_5		X	X	X
N_prM_1				
N_prM_2				
N_prM_3				
N_prM_4				
N_prM_5				

Supplementary Table 5. Summary of the evidence for recombination for Ebolavirus, for each coding region, sequence dataset, and replica.

	PhiPack			
	NSS	Chi^2	Phi (permutation)	Phi
A_GP		X		
A_L		X		
A_NP	X	X	X	X
A_sGP			X	X
A_vp24				
A_vp30	X			
A_vp35	X	X		
A_vp40				
N_GP				
N_L_1				
N_L_2		X		
N_L_3				
N_L_4		X		
N_L_5		X		
N_NP	X	X	X	X
N_sGP			X	X
N_VP24				
N_VP30	X			
N_VP35	X	X		
N_VP40				

Supplementary Table 6. Summary of the evidence for recombination for HIV1, for each coding region, sequence dataset, and replica.

	PhiPack			
	NSS	Chi ²	Phi (permutation)	Phi
A_ENV_1_1				
A_ENV_1_2				
A_ENV_1_3				
A_ENV_1_4				
A_ENV_1_5		X		
A_GAG_1_1	X			
A_GAG_1_2		X		
A_GAG_1_3			X	X
A_GAG_1_4		X		X
A_GAG_1_5		X	X	X
A_NEF_1_1		X	X	X
A_NEF_1_2			X	X
A_NEF_1_3			X	X
A_NEF_1_4				
A_NEF_1_5		X	X	X
A_POL_1_1				
A_POL_1_2			X	X
A_POL_1_3				X
A_POL_1_4	X			X
A_POL_1_5	X	X		X
A_REV_1_1		X		
A_REV_1_2		X		
A_REV_1_3		X		
A_REV_1_4				
A_REV_1_5		X		
A_TAT_1_1	X	X		
A_TAT_1_2	X	X		
A_TAT_1_3	X			
A_TAT_1_4	X			
A_TAT_1_5	X	X		
A_VIF_1_1		X		
A_VIF_1_2				
A_VIF_1_3	X			
A_VIF_1_4				
A_VIF_1_5				
A_VPR_1_1				
A_VPR_1_2	X			
A_VPR_1_3				
A_VPR_1_4				
A_VPR_1_5				
A_VPU_1_1			X	X
A_VPU_1_2	X	X	X	
A_VPU_1_3		X	X	X
A_VPU_1_4		X	X	X
A_VPU_1_5	X	X	X	X
N_ENV_1_1				
N_ENV_1_2				
N_ENV_1_3				
N_ENV_1_4				
N_ENV_1_5				
N_GAG_1_1			X	X
N_GAG_1_2				
N_GAG_1_3		X		X
N_GAG_1_4		X		X
N_GAG_1_5				X
N_NEF_1_1		X	X	X
N_NEF_1_2				
N_NEF_1_3				
N_NEF_1_4			X	X
N_NEF_1_5			X	X
N_POL_1_1				X
N_POL_1_2			X	X
N_POL_1_3			X	X
N_POL_1_4				
N_POL_1_5				X
N_REV_1_1		X		
N_REV_1_2		X		
N_REV_1_3				
N_REV_1_4		X		
N_REV_1_5				
N_TAT_1_1		X		
N_TAT_1_2		X		
N_TAT_1_3		X		
N_TAT_1_4	X			
N_TAT_1_5	X	X		
N_VIF_1_1	X			
N_VIF_1_2	X			
N_VIF_1_3		X		
N_VIF_1_4	X			
N_VIF_1_5	X			
N_VPR_1_1				
N_VPR_1_2				
N_VPR_1_3				
N_VPR_1_4	X	X		
N_VPR_1_5	X			
N_VPU_1_1	X	X		X
N_VPU_1_2	X	X	X	X
N_VPU_1_3		X		
N_VPU_1_4			X	X
N_VPU_1_5		X		

Supplementary Table 7. Location of HIV1 VPU positively selected amino acid sites per sequence dataset, and replica.

		Positively selected positions									
Replicas		2	3	5	7	24	27	72	73	76	78
Nucleotide	1	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow				
	2			Yellow	Yellow		Yellow				
	3			Yellow	Yellow		Yellow	Yellow			
	4	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow		Yellow		Yellow		
	5			Yellow	Yellow		Yellow	Yellow		Yellow	Yellow
Amino acid	1	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow				
	2			Yellow	Yellow		Yellow	Yellow			
	3	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow				
	4	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow		Yellow		Yellow	Yellow	
	5	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow		Yellow	Yellow		Yellow	Yellow

The first sequence of the first nucleotide replica was used as a reference.

Supplementary Table 8. Location of HIV1 VPR positively selected amino acid sites per sequence dataset, and replica.

		Positively selected positions											
Replicas		4	15	28	37	41	45	63	77	84	85	89	93
Nucleotide	1				■	■				■			■
	2		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	3			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	4				■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	5				■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Amino acid	1				■	■				■			■
	2	■		■	■	■	■		■	■			■
	3			■	■	■	■		■	■			■
	4	■		■	■	■	■		■	■		■	■
	5				■	■	■			■			■

The first sequence of the first nucleotide replica was used as a reference.

Supplementary Table 9. Location of HIV1 VIF positively selected amino acid sites per sequence dataset, and replica.

		Positively selected positions																		
Replicas		31	33	37	39	47	63	92	93	95	101	109	127	130	155	158	159	167	186	
Nucleotide	1	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	White	Yellow	Yellow	White									
	2	Yellow	White	White	White	White	White	Yellow	White	White	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	White	White	Yellow	Yellow	White	
	3	White	White	White	Yellow	White	Yellow	White	White	Yellow	White	Yellow								
	4	White	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	White	Yellow	White	White	White	White	Yellow	Yellow	White						
	5	White	White	White	White	Yellow	White	White	White	White	White	Yellow	White	Yellow	White	White	White	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Amino acid	1	Yellow	White	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	White	White	White	Yellow	Yellow	White	White	Yellow	White	Yellow	Yellow	White	
	2	Yellow	White	White	White	White	Yellow	White	White	White	Yellow	White	Yellow	White	White	White	White	Yellow	Yellow	
	3	White	White	White	White	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	White	White	Yellow	White	White	White	Yellow	White	White	White	
	4	White	White	White	White	White	White	Yellow	White	Yellow	Yellow									
	5	White	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	White	Yellow	White	White	White	White	Yellow	White	White	White	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	

The first sequence of the first nucleotide replica was used as a reference.

Supplementary Table 10. Location of HIV1 TAT positively selected amino acid sites per sequence dataset, and replica.

		Positively selected positions																															
Replicas		7	19	21	23	24	29	32	36	39	40	58	60	61	63	64	67	68	69	70	74	75	76	77	78	80	81	87	97	99	100	101	
Nucleotide	1																																
	2																																
	3																																
	4																																
	5																																
Amino acid	1																																
	2																																
	3																																
	4																																
	5																																

The first sequence of the first nucleotide replica was used as a reference.

Supplementary Table 11. Location of HIV1 REV positively selected amino acid sites per sequence dataset, and replica.

		Positively selected positions																			
Replicas		11	14	15	18	21	28	30	31	53	54	57	61	62	63	67	68	82	86	91	99
Nucleotide	1		■		■		■	■		■	■			■		■	■	■			
	2		■		■		■		■	■				■		■	■	■			
	3		■	■			■		■	■	■					■	■	■		■	
	4	■			■		■		■		■			■	■	■	■	■	■		■
	5				■	■	■		■		■		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Amino acid	1		■		■	■		■	■	■	■		■	■	■	■	■	■			■
	2		■		■			■	■	■	■		■	■	■	■	■	■			■
	3				■		■		■	■	■		■	■	■	■	■	■			■
	4		■		■		■		■	■	■		■	■	■	■	■	■	■		■
	5	■	■		■	■	■		■		■		■	■	■	■	■	■	■		■

The first sequence of the first nucleotide replica was used as a reference.

Supplementary Table 12. Location of HIV1 POL positively selected amino acid sites per sequence dataset, and replica.

		Positively selected positions																																																		
Replicas		17	21	32	34	37	38	39	40	45	48	50	54	55	56	66	75	119	278	290	317	328	362	366	370	400	441	489	512	531	532	590	607	623	638	646	709	732	787	816	834	839										
Nucleotide	1	Y																Y	Y																																	
	2	Y																	Y	Y																																
	3	Y																	Y	Y																																
	4	Y																	Y	Y																																
	5	Y																	Y	Y																																
Amino acid	1	Y																Y	Y																																	
	2	Y																	Y	Y																																
	3	Y																	Y	Y																																
	4	Y																	Y	Y																																
	5	Y																	Y	Y																																

The first sequence of the first nucleotide replica was used as a reference.

Supplementary Table 13. Location of HIV1 NEF positively selected amino acid sites per sequence dataset, and replica.

		Positively selected positions														
Replicas		8	14	15	35	65	96	113	144	162	172	191	197	203	207	211
Nucleotide	1			■				■	■		■	■	■	■	■	■
	2			■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	3			■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	4			■	■		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	5			■	■		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Amino acid	1			■			■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■
	2	■		■			■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■
	3	■	■	■			■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■
	4	■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	5	■	■	■			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

The first sequence of the first nucleotide replica was used as a reference.

Supplementary Table 14. Location of HIV1 GAG positively selected amino acid sites per sequence dataset, and replica.

		Positively selected positions																															
Replicas		15	28	54	61	67	69	79	84	90	91	93	121	122	143	212	220	249	277	300	329	354	368	369	370	381	466	467	471	477	488		
Nucleotide	1																																
	2																																
	3																																
	4																																
	5																																
Amino acid	1																																
	2																																
	3																																
	4																																
	5																																

The first sequence of the first nucleotide replica was used as a reference.

Supplementary Table 10. Analysis of 1000 Genes (randomly selected genes) and their gene expression levels and patterns

Gene	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100
Gene 1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.0	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.7	3.8	3.9	4.0	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4	4.5	4.6	4.7	4.8	4.9	5.0	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	5.7	5.8	5.9	6.0	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.5	6.6	6.7	6.8	6.9	7.0	7.1	7.2	7.3	7.4	7.5	7.6	7.7	7.8	7.9	8.0	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	8.5	8.6	8.7	8.8	8.9	9.0	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4	9.5	9.6	9.7	9.8	9.9	10.0
Gene 2	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.0	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.7	3.8	3.9	4.0	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4	4.5	4.6	4.7	4.8	4.9	5.0	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	5.7	5.8	5.9	6.0	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.5	6.6	6.7	6.8	6.9	7.0	7.1	7.2	7.3	7.4	7.5	7.6	7.7	7.8	7.9	8.0	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	8.5	8.6	8.7	8.8	8.9	9.0	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4	9.5	9.6	9.7	9.8	9.9	10.0
Gene 3	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.0	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.7	3.8	3.9	4.0	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4	4.5	4.6	4.7	4.8	4.9	5.0	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	5.7	5.8	5.9	6.0	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.5	6.6	6.7	6.8	6.9	7.0	7.1	7.2	7.3	7.4	7.5	7.6	7.7	7.8	7.9	8.0	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	8.5	8.6	8.7	8.8	8.9	9.0	9.1	9.2	9.3	9.4	9.5	9.6	9.7	9.8	9.9	10.0

Supplementary Figure 1. Linear regression of running times and p (the number of sequences times the number of ungapped codons) for Zika (A), Dengue (B), Ebolavirus (C), and HIV1 (D) analyses. The amount of variability explained (R^2), as well as the regression equation is shown for each codeML model (M0, M1a, M2a, M3, M7 and M8). All correlations are significant at $P < 0.001$.

Supplementary Figure 2. Linear regression of running times and coding regions total variability levels for Zika (A), Dengue (B), Ebolavirus (C), and HIV1 (D) analyses. The amount of variability explained (R^2), as well as the regression equation is shown for each codeML model (M0, M1a, M2a, M3, M7 and M8). For Zika, for models M1a, M2a, M7 and M8 the correlations are significant at $P < 0.001$; for models M0 and M3 at $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.01$, respectively. For Dengue, the only significant correlations are those for models M2a, M3 and M8 at $P < 0.05$. For Ebolavirus, the only significant correlation is that for model M7 at $P < 0.05$. For HIV1, all correlations are significant at $P < 0.001$.

Supplementary Figure 3. Linear regression between coding region size (number of codons) and total variability levels (in percentage). For Zika, the correlation is significant at $P < 0.001$, while for Ebolavirus and HIV1 is significant at $P < 0.01$. For Dengue (underlined) the correlation is non-significant ($P > 0.05$).

Supplementary Figure 4. Power function showing the correlation between running times and sequence number for OmegaMap.